

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILY VIOLENCE AND METHODS OF PREVENTION

¹Khamrakulova Kamola Gayratovna

Is a doctoral student of Gulistan State University,

²Akhmadjonova Kamola Ilhomjonovna

Is a student of the Nizomiy State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7457690>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th December 2022

Accepted: 18th December 2022

Online: 19th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Family, family relations, family values, transformation, problem identification, conceptualization, formalization, implementation, testing.

ABSTRACT

This article is focused on the analysis of socio-psychological characteristics of family violence and methods of prevention. Even in today's rapidly changing era of globalization, Uzbekistan considers its perspective and future to be in the development of the family, honoring it, enriching our traditional values and creating a modern, exemplary and prosperous family. It is also evident when construction has become one of the priority directions of state policy.

Even in today's rapidly changing era of globalization, the fact that Uzbekistan considers its perspective and future to be in the development and honoring of the family is evident when the creation of a modern, exemplary and prosperous family, enriching our traditional values, has become one of the priorities of the state policy. One of the most relevant and promising directions in modern psychology is the study of the family and the changes that occur in it. The researchers' interest in this problem is determined by the crisis situations occurring in the life of modern families and their impact on other areas of society. At present, among young people, ideas about marriage and family, distribution of roles in the family are undergoing certain changes. A transformation of family values is taking place, leading to an increase in the number of family separations, premarital births and dysfunctional families. Psychological

support is of great importance in preventing such situations and finding a solution to the problem. One of the most urgent and important issues in providing psychological assistance to families is the implementation of a correct psychological diagnosis. Diagnostics of family relations helps to identify effective ways and methods for solving family problems. Test methods are often used to reveal the internal environment of the family, the hidden psychological reasons and laws that lead to the emergence of problematic situations. Today, in psychology, there are a number of methods aimed at determining marriage-family relations. But nevertheless, the most sensitive issue in the field of family counseling is to be able to get complete, accurate and objective information about the client's family-marriage relationship. Accurate diagnosis, correct selection of corrective work direction and methods, as well as the

effectiveness of the provided assistance depend on this information. According to the experience of developing an expert system, the process of creating a psychodiagnostic system can be divided into 5 stages[1]: 1. Identification of the problem - at this stage, the task is clarified, a source of knowledge related to the problem is found (books, information from experts, methods). 2. Conceptualization - the system of acquired knowledge is formed at this stage: a list of basic concepts is compiled, connections between concepts, and logical judgments are developed. The task of the conceptualization stage is to describe knowledge in an informal way, in which the main concepts and relationships between concepts are presented in the form of graphs, tables, diagrams. 3. Formalization - the concepts of the studied area are formed, logical methods and effective models are selected. 4. Realization - there should be a special product of its own to create an expertly prepared and formed knowledge base. the main task of this stage is to develop a software package through instrumental means. 5. Testing - it is used to check the operation of the created expert system, whether it meets the vital requirements, and to identify the mistakes made in the previous stages. . Family diagnosis is an assessment of the family system, which helps to identify conditions that may cause somatic or neurotic disorders in family members. There are various methods of diagnosis: projective, blank, game, etc. There are also different directions in family therapy (strategic, structural, dynamic, behavioral, etc.), each of which has its own methods of family diagnosis. In order to achieve the goal set in family diagnostics, it is important to solve the following tasks: -

review the state of the problem of family relations in modern scientific and popular literature; - clarification of methods of diagnosis of marriage-family relations; - to show the general and specific aspects and practical significance of the proposed methods; - to clarify the purpose and manner of research on family relations using psychodiagnostic methods. To study the phenomenon of family relations, psychologists recommend the following methods: ROP, PEA, "Conflicts" questionnaires, as well as family relations test (FBT) and T. Leary test. It is known that many methods are aimed at studying family relations and the roles of the spouses in the family, which show mutual expectations and aspirations. As one of these methods, N.V. Volkova's "Role Expectations and Aspirations in the Family" (ROP) method can be taken. In this methodology, a number of family values are presented, and the couple's attitude to this value system, that is, their aspirations and expectations from their spouse, are determined and compared. The purpose of the methodology: □ It is to clarify the perceptions of the spouses about the common personality characteristics of the couple in family life, parental obligations, sexual relations, professional interests of each, daily housekeeping, moral and emotional support, external attractiveness of the spouse. These indicators reflect the main functions of the family and make up the scale of family values (FSS). □ It consists in determining the perceptions of couples about the distribution of male and female roles in the family, which is reflected in the scale of role expectations and aspirations (RKISH). Thus, the results of this methodology help to determine the hierarchy of family values of the husband

and wife, as well as to draw a conclusion about the socio-psychological compatibility of the couple in the family. The methodology "Role expectations and aspirations in the family" consists of two options (for men and women) and 36 points in each, consisting of 7 scales. As mentioned above, the methodology is aimed at determining role expectations and aspirations in the family, where role expectation is a couple's attitude to expect their spouse to fulfill family obligations, while role aspiration is personal readiness to fulfill family roles. In addition, the PEA questionnaire developed by A.N. Volkova, this methodology helps to diagnose three phenomena: understanding of the partner, emotional attraction and respect for the spouse [2; P.14-15]. Each scale of the methodology consists of 15 questions. The perception scale helps to determine the degree to which the image of the spouse is formed in the eyes of the client. Emotional attraction is determined through projective questions and shows the emotional relationship towards the spouse. And the respect scale helps to make a conclusion about his reputation, importance and reference in the eyes of his spouse. The T. Leary test is used to diagnose how they mutually understand the image of an ideal spouse. FBT - Family Relationship Test - is a projective technique first described in 1936 by Howells and Likorish. It contains a collection of 40 pictures depicting various relationships between family members. The test is aimed at obtaining information

about a person's attitude towards family members [3]. According to psychologists, a family with a healthy psychologically stable environment can be characterized as follows: similarity of family values, high adequacy of roles, few conflicts in various aspects of life, high mutual respect and emotional pleasantness. This formula was developed in 1982. One of the most important aspects of providing psychological support to the family is to change the assumptions established in the minds of couples, and to teach them how to respond appropriately to life situations, including relationships with their spouses. It is necessary to explain to the spouses the nature and essence of conflict situations, to show the methods and ways of constructively solving them. There will be life problems that cannot be solved. In such situations, it is appropriate to change the attitude towards them, to teach them a new psychological perception while softening their unpleasant sides a little. Through the research conducted by psychologists of our country and abroad on marriage-family relations, it can be concluded that people cannot be made happy by force, but with the help of psychodiagnostic methods developed and approved by experts, on the basis of a comprehensive approach, the study of marriage-family relations can be professionally organized and consulted. we are sure that providing support will go some way to mending broken family relationships.

References:

1. Trofimova I.N. "Prognozirovanie povedeniya cheloveka kak zadacha ekspertnoy psychodiagnosticheskoi sistemy" / "Voprosy psikhologii", 1994, No. 3.
2. Chalov V.N., Belyalova M.A., Moroz V.A. Diagnostics suprujeskikh otnosheniy. Method. posobie. Krasnodar, 2016. - 198 p.

3. Materialy » Spetsializirovannye psichologicheskie metodiki diagnostici vnutrisemeynyx otnosheniy. <http://www.psworks.ru>
4. Aleshina Yu.E., Gozman L.Ya. Dubovskaya E.M. Sotsialno-psichologicheskie metody issledovaniya sprujeskikh otnosheniy. Spetspraktikum po sotsialnoy psichologii. - M.: MGU, 1987. - 126p.
5. Isaeva M. PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS OF FAMILY RELATIONS //Internauka. - 2020. - No. 23-3. - S. 63-66.
6. Relationship of functional asymmetry with individual psychological features of the personality. The Way of Science International scientific journal, No. 4 (86), 2021. ISSN 2311-2158. Impact factor of the journal "The Way of Science" - 0.543 (Global Impact Factor, Australia). P.85-89.
7. Nazarov A. S. Psychological aspects of managerial decision making // Molodoy uchenyy. - 2020. - No. 44. - S. 45-48.